

Some new insect pests of rice in Uttar Pradesh, India

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Surveys conducted during 1981-84 revealed the presence of several insect pests not previously reported on upland rice in the hills of Uttar Pradesh (see table). Most of these pests have

recorded low economic loss, but their occurrence indicates that they could become serious pests under favorable climatic conditions.

Of the insects found, shootfly caused 22-25% deadhearts in the nursery in 1983. Small grasshoppers were abundant throughout the 1984 season. Other insects remained at a low level.

The Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London, confirmed the insect identification. *J*

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Insect and year when first recorded	Order:Family	Damage
Horned caterpillar <i>Melanitis leda</i> Linnaeus 1981 ^a	Lepidoptera:Satyridae	Larvae feed on leaf blade.
Tussock caterpillar <i>Euproctis</i> sp. probably <i>Virguncula</i> Walker 1981	Lepidoptera:Lymantriidae	Larvae are defoliators.
Bombay locust <i>Patanga succincta</i> (Linnaeus) 1982	Orthoptera:Acrididae	Nymph and adults feed on leaves.
Small grasshopper <i>Oxya japonica japonica</i> (Thunberg) 1982	Orthoptera:Acrididae	Nymphs and adults feed on leaves.
Aphid <i>Hysteroneura setariae</i> (Thomas) 1982	Homoptera:Aphididae	Feeds on shoots and developing panicles.
Green leafhopper <i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i> (Stal.) 1981	Homoptera:Cicadellidae	Nymphs and adults suck sap from leaves.
Leafhopper <i>Psammotettix striatus</i> (Linne) 1981	Homoptera:Cicadellidae	Nymphs and adults suck sap from leaves in nursery seedlings.
Leaf fly <i>Oscinella</i> sp. 1981	Diptera:Chloropidae	Larvae cause whitish hollow outgrowths of interval leaf.
Earwig <i>Elaeum bipartitus</i> (Kirby) 1981	Dermaptera:Forficulidae	Adults observed on panicles.
Flea beetle <i>Chaetocnema basalis</i> (Baly) 1982	Coleoptera:Chrysomelidae	Adults feed on leaves by biting holes in them.
Shootfly <i>Atherigona oryzae</i> Mall. 1983	Diptera:Muscidae	Maggots feed on central shoot of seedlings.
Pollen beetle <i>Chiloloba acuta</i> (Wiedemann) 1982	Coleoptera:Scarabaeidae	Adults are observed as pollen feeders.

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Predators of rice caseworm

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The leaf tube constructed by rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* protects the larvae from natural enemies. Larval parasitization is always below 5%. The role of aquatic predators was assessed in greenhouse trials.

Caseworm larvae caged in potted plants immersed in water were offered as prey to a range of aquatic insects collected from reservoirs, canals, and ricefields. Two predatory groups were revealed. The larvae of *Sternolophus rufipes* (Fabricius), a hydrophilid, stalk caseworm larvae underwater and seize them as they stretch out of their protective cases while swimming. Sometimes the predator entered the case to locate the caseworm. The larva of *Cybister tripunctatus orientalis* Gschwendtner, a dytiscid, holds onto a submerged object waiting for prey to swim overhead. It rises quickly to the surface and seizes the outstretched caseworm larva. Younger dytiscids enter the case while older ones seize the case with powerful, sickle-shaped mandibles, forcing the caseworm larvae out.

Single dytiscid or hydrophilid larvae that were offered caseworm larvae of a range of ages in no-choice tests showed preference for older prey (see table).

Capacity of aquatic beetle larvae to prey on rice caseworm larvae in no-choice tests. IRRI greenhouse, 1984.

Caseworm larval instar	Caseworm larvae consumed (no./d)		
	Hydrophilid ^a instar IV	Dytiscid ^b	
		Instar II	Instar IV
I	2.2 c	4.8 b	4.0 b
II	2.8 bc	4.8 b	4.0 b
III	4.5 ab	8.4 ab	9.0 ab
IV	5.2 ab	10.0 ab	10.8 a
V	6.7 a	11.6 a	11.4 a

^aAv of 5 replications; single predator larva offered 15 prey. ^bAv of 6 replications; single predator larva offered 25 prey.

The hydrophilid larva consumed up to 6.7 fifth-instar caseworm larvae daily, but only 2-3 of first- or second-instar larvae. Regardless of age, the dytiscid preferred older prey. It was also more voracious, consuming more than 11

fifth-instar caseworm larvae daily.

Aquatic predators may explain why caseworm is more prevalent in rainfed than in irrigated wetlands. Rice irrigated from rivers, reservoirs, or canals would already contain dytiscids

and hydrophilids. Delayed dispersal flights of predators to rainfed fields could allow greater survival of the caseworm, which attacks a young crop before the aquatic predators can initiate a new infestation. *S*

Major insect pests of rice in Cuba

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Rice planthopper *Sogatodes orizicola*, the hoja blanca virus vector, is the principal insect pest of rice in Cuba (see table). Life cycle of adult males is 14-24 d; that of females, 27-31 d. The cycle from egg to adult is about 25 d. *S. orizicola* needs high temperatures (25-27°C) for optimum development.

Higher insect activity and population densities are Apr-Nov.

The most difficult insect pest to control is the rice water weevil, with a 50-d cycle from oviposition to adult emergence. Adults live an average 714 d. *Lissorhoptrus brevirostris* population is highest in Apr-Nov, with large damages to ricefields.

Other important pests are rice stink bug *Oebalus insularis* and fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda*.

Other insects are sporadic pests of rice in Cuba. *S*

First meiotic chromosomes of male *Nephotettix malayanus*

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During growth phase of spermatogenesis in the green leafhopper *N. malayanus*, the primary spermatocytes undergo the first meiotic division. At diakinesis (Fig. 1a), the maximum condensation and coiling of holokinetic chromosomes results in 6 synapsed homologs plus a univalent X-body.

The male *N. malayanus* therefore has the normal diploid complement, $2n = 13$ ($6I_A + X$). The prospective haploid sperm cells are of two types: ($6I_A + X$) and ($6I_A$). The darkly stained, unpaired X-chromosome measured 1.18μ in length and width, and was usually isolated from the bivalent autosomes.

In pachytene analysis of meiotic chromosomes, the mean total

Major insect pests of lowland rice in Cuba, 1976-84.

Scientific name	Growth stage	Damage	Infestation (%)
<i>Sogatodes orizicola</i> (Muir) (Homoptera: Delphacidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf sucking (nymphs and adults)	2-12
<i>Sogatodes cubanus</i> (Crawford) (Homoptera: Delphacidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf sucking (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Lissorhoptrus brevirostris</i> (Suffr.) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Root feeding (larvae) Leaf feeding on leaves (adults)	10-28
<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i> (F. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf feeding (larvae) May eat entire plant	6-10
<i>Hortensia similis</i> (Walk.) (Homoptera: Cicadellidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf sucking (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Draeculacephala cubana</i> (M & B) (Homoptera: Cicadellidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf sucking (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Hydrellia</i> sp. (Diptera: Ephydriidae)	Emergence to panicle initiation	Feeding on tissue along the inner margins of emerging leaves (larvae)	New pests
<i>Diatraea saccharalis</i> (F.) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae)	Emergence to panicle initiation	Feeding within the stem, severing the vascular system (larvae)	
<i>Caulopsis cuspidatus</i> (Scud.) (Orthoptera: Acrididae)	Panicle initiation to heading	Feeding on the leaf blade	
<i>Conocephalus</i> [= <i>Xiphidium</i>] <i>fasciatus</i> (De Geer) (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae)	Panicle initiation to heading	Leaf feeding (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Conocephaloides obscurelus</i> (De Geer) (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae)	Panicle initiation to heading	Leaf feeding (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Schistocerca pallens</i> (Thunb.) (Orthoptera: Acrididae)	Panicle initiation to heading	Defoliate plants	
<i>Oebalus insularis</i> (Stal) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae)	Milk stage	Sucking each grain (nymphs and adults)	3-17

1. Chromosomes of male *N. malayanus* at a) diakinesis showing $2n = 13$, and b) metaphase I. Spontaneous aberration may result in c) an agmatoploid cell with $2n = 19$ ($9II + X$). IRRI, 1985-86. Arrow indicates the sex chromosome. Magnification 1500X (oil immersion).